

QUIZ

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COURSE CODE : ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 6
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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: ACADEMIC WRITING

- 1. The most experienced researcher chose one of the following types of questions as it helps them to explore more a sequential “so what?” Questions?**
 - Practical questions
 - Conceptual questions¹**
 - Theoretical question
 - Practical and theoretical questions
- 2. There are two different types of citation styles namely author-date style and note bibliography, according to the note bibliography style in which one of the following sequences is correct?**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16-17.

- Author's last name, date of publication, the title of the book: subtitle of the book(place of publication: publisher name), page number
 - Author last and first name, the title of the book: subtitle of the book (place of publication: publisher name, date of publication), page number²**
 - Theoretical question
 - Practical and theoretical questions
3. **In academic writing, citation plays a significant role in different aspect; one of the most important purposes of citation is**
- To make our writing more attractive
 - To influence our readers
 - To avoid plagiarism³**
 - To show favor for the author
4. **Once after determining our research topic, there is a need to ask a serious of questions to understand more. A tentative answer to the research question referred to as:**
- Research question
 - Working hypothesis⁴**
 - Problem statement
 - Goal setting

² Turabian, 90.

³ Laurent, Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 10.

⁴ Turabian, 21.

5. **Once we set out our hypothesis, we need to review the literature to understand what is known and what needs to be discovered more in the area of our research topic. To collect adequate information, we need to develop a guiding tool referred as:**

- Developing a master board
- Boulding storyboard
- Conceptual framework**⁵
- Analytical framework

6. **The process of writing qualitative dissertation is not a leaner process instead, it is a cyclic iterative process where some times unpredictable. In this process which one of the following shows the beginning and the last steps in an ideal situation.**

- Reading, planning, writing, conducting, collecting data, analysis, interpreting, concluding and recommendation**⁶
- Planning, reading, writing, conducting, collecting data, analyzing, interpreting, concluding and recommendation
- Reading, writing, planning, conducting, collecting data, analyzing, interpreting, concluding and recommendation
- Reading, writing, planning, collecting data, conducting, analyzing, interpreting, concluding and recommendation

7. **In qualitative study our research approach will be determined by one of the following important topic**

- The literature review we have done

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and F. Volpe Marie, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc, 2008), 82.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, 1.

- Research problem**⁷
- Our research audience
- Interest of our school

8. **According to WHO style of writing which one of the following title written correctly?**

- Professor**⁸
- Prof
- Prof.
- Prof,

9. **Which punctuation sign give more pouse or more definite break than comma?**

- Colon
- Full stop
- Semi colon**⁹
- Question mark

10. **According to WHO style guide, there are some words which are not preferred to use, select one.**

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: WHO, 2004), 35.

⁹ WHO Style Guide, 22.

- Ongoing¹⁰
- Oral
- Offensive
- Order

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: WHO, 2004.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ WHO style guide, 50.